

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THE MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF RECYCLED CFRP

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SUMMARY

The mechanical behaviour of a recycled CFRP (rCFRP), with fibres reclaimed by pyrolysis and manufactured via resin infusion of recycled-fibre mats, is studied. The mechanical properties are characterised, demonstrating that rCFRP can replace GFRP. The rCFRP failure modes in tension and compression are also investigated, at the microcopic scale.

Keywords: recycling, CFRP, experimental testing, material characterisation, failure.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the increasing amount of carbon fibres (CF) produced [1], the recent environmental legislation on the disposal of end-of-life vehicles [2], and the high value and limited availability of CF [3], recycling routes for CF reinforced-polymers (CFRPs) have been investigated. As a result, several recycling processes – mechanical [4], thermal [1,5,6] and chemical [7] – are now available and entering into a mature stage of development.

However, the knowledge on the mechanical behaviour of the recycled CFRPs (rCFRPs) is still limited [8,9], so these novel materials cannot be fully considered for structural design yet. Therefore, investigating experimentally the behaviour of the recyclate and developing structural design methods is necessary to close the loop in the life cycle of CFRPs.

This paper presents an experimental investigation on the structural response of a rCFRP. In the first section, the material is identified in terms of its precursor, fibre-reclaiming method, and composite-manufacturing process. The second section describes the procedures carried out to analyse the microstructure of the rCFRP, to characterise the mechanical properties, and to investigate the failure modes. The experimental results are presented in the fourth section, and discussed in the fifth section. Finally, the main conclusions are summarised.

MATERIAL SYSTEM

The material studied in this investigation is a rCFRP [10]. The precursor material (from which the fibres were reclaimed) was a woven pre-preg obtained from Boeing's manufacturing scrap, with Toray T300 reinforcement and epoxy matrix. The geometry and mechanical properties of the virgin carbon-fibres are given in Table 1 [10].

The carbon-fibres were reclaimed by Milled Carbon, through their proprietary pyrolysis process [1]. The rCF geometry and mechanical properties also included in Table 1 [10].

Recycled-fibre mats were produced via a papermaking technique. Plates of recycled composite were then manufactured through resin-film infusion with ACG XMTM 257 epoxy matrix [10]. The reinforcement is in a randomly-oriented short-fibre architecture (although the orientation of the fibres is not isotropic), with nominal fibre volume content of $V_f = 30\%$. The void content in the plates ranges from $V_v = 5\%$ to 8% .

Each plate is approximately 2.5 mm thick, and has all the fibre-mats oriented in the same direction (relatively to the manufacturing process). The surface presents no significant waviness or excessive roughness, but the thickness varies linearly along the edges (up to 20% thickness variation within a length of 150 mm).

Table 1 – Fibre diameter (ϕ_f), stiffness (E_f) and strength ($X_{f,T}$) of virgin and recycled carbon-fibres (gauge length: 6 mm) [10].

Carbon fibres	ϕ_f (μm)	E_f (GPa)	$X_{f,T}$ (GPa)
virgin	7.03	227.80	4.24
recycled	7.20	217.79	4.16
variation (recycled over virgin)	+2.4%	-4.4%	-1.9%

PROCEDURES

Microstructure

The microstructure of the rCFRP was studied qualitatively through optical microscopy, with amplifications ranging from $2.5\times$ to $50\times$; this study comprised both the in-plane and the through-the-thickness plate directions. The specimen surface analysed was polished in consecutively finer media, up to a $1\ \mu\text{m}$ diamond solution.

Mechanical characterisation

The rCFRP mechanical properties for in-plane tension (subscript T) and compression (subscript C) were determined; for each case, at least 5 specimens were tested, both for longitudinal (superscript 1) and transverse (superscript 2) directions (relatively to manufacture). The specimens were cut with a diamond wet saw, and $\pm 45^\circ$ glass-fibre end-tabs (1.5 mm thick) were bonded with a 3M Scotch-Weld 9323 B/A adhesive.

The tensile tests followed the ASTM 3039 standard [11]; Table 2 defines the nominal specimen geometry, the strain gauges used, and the test displacement rate.

Table 2 – Specimen geometry, instrumentation and test speed for the mechanical characterisation.

Test	Gauge length (mm)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	End-tab edge	Strain gauges	Disp. rate (mm/min)
Tension	70	150	25	90° or 45°	FCA-6-11 (T1) FLA-6-11 (T2)	1
Compression	7	90	19	-45° with adhesive fillet	2 \times YEFLA-2	1

The compression tests followed the ICSTM standard [12]; Table 2 defines the nominal specimen geometry, the strain gauges used, and the test displacement rate. The strength X_C and extension at failure $\varepsilon_{C_{failure}}$ were computed taking into account the bending at the end of the test, so (considering load P and extensions ε positive for compression):

$$\varepsilon_{C_{failure}} = \max(\varepsilon_{failure}^{front}, \varepsilon_{failure}^{back}) \quad X_C = \frac{P}{A} + E_{failure} \cdot \varepsilon_{failure}^{bending},$$

where the stiffness at failure $E_{failure}$ is the tangent modulus for the ultimate 0.2% deformation, and the bending deformation is $\varepsilon_{failure}^{bending} = \varepsilon_{C_{failure}} - \varepsilon_{failure}^{average}$.

Investigation of failure modes

The rCFRP failure modes in tension and compression were investigated via microscopical observation of loaded and unloaded specimens.

The geometries of the specimens are shown in Figure 1.a-b. The geometry of the notch was selected to ensure stable crack propagation. The pre-crack extension (in dashed line) was not cut in all specimens. To prevent outwards buckling in the compression investigation, some specimens had angled loading surfaces (dashed line, Figure 1.b) so as to move the load line upwards.

The test setups are shown in Figure 1.c. The same loading rig was used both for compression and tension, adding in the latter case a wedge (wrapped in a PTFE insert) to open the notch. The longitudinal and transverse directions were both investigated.

The in-plane surface of each tensile specimen was observed in an optical microscope, while loaded. For the compression specimens, a similar observation was done first; afterwards, the cross section of the post-mortem unload specimens was observed as well.

Figure 1 – Specimen geometry and test setup for the investigation of failure modes.

RESULTS

Microstructure

Figure 2 shows representative in-plane and through-the-thickness sections of the composite. It is seen that fibres are strongly oriented in-plane (Figure 2.a vs. Figure 2.b), and slightly aligned in the longitudinal (1) direction (opposed to direction 2 in Figure 2.a). Fibre length is considerably variable.

Figure 2 – Typical microstructure of the rCFRP.

Figure 3 shows some distinct features identified in the recycled material: (a) presence of fibre bundles; (b) through-the-thickness fibre waviness (c) broken fibres prior to loading and (d) high void content.

Figure 3 – Distinct features of the rCFRP microstructure.

Standard mechanical characterisation

Tables 3 to 5 present the mechanical properties measured for the recycled material. Figure 4 shows typical stress vs. strain curves, obtained in the four directions tested. The tensile response of the material is reasonably linear, while for compression a marked non-linear behavior is observed; the material is also considerably stronger and more ductile in compression than in tension. Both the stiffness and the strength are higher in the longitudinal (1) direction than in the transverse (2) direction.

Table 3 – Elastic properties.

Property	E_T^1 (GPa)	E_T^2 (GPa)	E_C^1 (GPa)	E_C^2 (GPa)	ν_{12}
Average	29.4	15.8	25.6	15.4	0.42
CoV	4.8%	3.2%	1.8%	6.1%	2.1%

Table 4 – Failure strengths.

Property	X_T^1 (MPa)	X_T^2 (MPa)	X_C^1 (MPa)	X_C^2 (MPa)
Average	208.5	120.6	358.3	285.0
CoV	6.9%	10.9%	3.0%	2.3%

Table 5 – Extension at failure.

Property	ε_T^1 (%)	ε_T^2 (%)	ε_C^1 (%)	ε_C^2 (%)
Average	0.73	0.79	1.76	2.71
CoV	7.0%	13.3%	3.5%	13.8%

Figure 4 – Typical stress – strain curves for the mechanical characterization tests.

The tensile specimens failed near one of the end tabs in a rough surface, sometimes with one small piece of material pulled-out (Figures 5.a-b). The macroscopic failure path along the thickness is approximately normal to the loading direction; on the contrary, the in-plane failure line is irregular and curved, especially for the longitudinal specimens (Figure 5.a). No improvement on the strength was noticed when using angled end-tabs instead of straight ones.

The compression specimens failed in the gauge section (Figure 5.c). Two rough failure surfaces, angled in the through-the-thickness direction, were generally observable, usually with one small piece of material pulled-out; the in-plane failure line is also curved and irregular. No difference was observed between the longitudinal and transverse failure paths.

Figure 5 – Typical failure of the specimens used for mechanical characterization.

Investigation of failure modes

Under tension, the rCFRP fails by formation of a brittle crack (Figure 6); this crack follows an irregular path at the microscopic scale, but is relatively straight at a macroscopic scale (Figure 6.a). The propagation path follows (i) previously-broken (during manufacture) fibre-sections and (ii) the fibre-matrix interface (Figure 6.b); no formation of new failure surfaces in fibres was observed. The failure mechanisms in the longitudinal and transverse directions appear to be very similar (Figure 6.c).

Figure 6 – Results from the investigation of tensile failure. (Crack propagates downwards.)

a.1) Band orientation

a) Shear band formed at the notch, in longitudinal specimen

a.2) Fibre bending with no fibre failure

b.1) Band orientation

b) Shear band formed at the notch, in transverse specimen

b.2) No fibres aligned with the band

c.1) Overview

c) Shear band formed at the loading edge, in transverse specimen

c.2) Rotation of broken fibre segments

d) Separation of segments of a broken fibre, in bending (in-plane, loaded micrograph)

e) Fibre-matrix interface failure

Figure 7 – Results from the investigation of compressive failure. (Vertical loading.) Unless mentioned otherwise, the micrographs were taken on the cross section, unload.

Under compression, the rCFRP fails by forming through-the-thickness shear bands (Figure 7), visible both at the specimen in-plane surface and cross section; these are consistently initiated near the notch (Figure 7.a-b), and also occasionally on the loading edges (Figure 7.c). When fibres aligned with the loading are in the path of a shear band, fibre bending occurs (Figure 7.a.1); if broken (prior to loading) fibre segments exist, they rotate and align themselves with the sheared matrix (Figure 7.c.2); the fibre-matrix interface fails as well, especially for the later stages of band formation (Figure 7.e). The bands are inclined in relation to the normal to the load direction (Figure 7.a-c), with lower angles observed for the areas with higher fibre alignment in the load direction (Figure 7.a.1).

DISCUSSION

Comparison with other materials

Figure 8 compares the mechanical properties of the rCFRP studied in this paper and those of other materials.

Relatively to virgin materials, Figure 8.a shows that the mechanical properties of the rCFRP studied are clearly superior to those of an isotropic glass-phenol composite with $V_f = 31\%$; this is one of the most used composite in aircraft interiors [8], meaning that the rCFRP could have a similar application with significant mass savings. Comparatively to an aerospace grade 2024-T4 Aluminium alloy [8], the rCFRP is softer and also weaker in tension, but stronger (in specific terms) in compression; this reveals that there is scope for using rCFRPs in typical aluminium applications, but also that it is required to develop and establish novel design methods to account for the particularities of the recycle mechanical behaviour and make full use of its potential.

Relatively to other rCFRP, Figure 8.b compares the response of the recycle studied in this paper (in the longitudinal direction) with those analysed by Wong et al [8] and Allen [9]. It shows that very diverse properties are obtained – especially strength – although the single-fibre tensile properties, the matrix properties, the manufacturing process, the fibre volume content and the fibre architecture of the rCFRP are similar (or suggest an opposite trend) [8,9]. Given that (i) the three rCFRPs compared use fibres reclaimed by different processes and (ii) the tensile failure mode of the rCFRP here studied is dominated by fibre-matrix interface failure, it is suggested that the surface quality of the rCFs is a key factor for the tensile strength of the recycled composite.

Figure 8 – Comparison of mechanical properties between the studied rCFRP and other materials.

Tensile failure

Specifically in relation to tensile failure mechanisms, it was found that the interfacial strength of the fibres – which is defined by the fibre surface and therefore by the carbon-fibre reclaiming process – plays a critical role. In addition, failure is also influenced by the presence of broken fibres prior to loading (Figure 6.b); this fibre breakage should occur during the manufacturing of the composite plates, meaning that improvements on the rCFRP performance should result both from improvement of (i) the interfacial strength of fibres and (ii) the compaction process.

The preferred fibre orientation along the longitudinal direction (Figure 2.a) justifies the stiffer response of the material in that direction, comparatively to the transverse one. The results of the standard tensile tests in the two directions suggest that failure is defined by the level of strain, regardless of the material direction (Table 5 and Figure 4); this supports the hypothesis of a failure mechanism that is independent of the single-fibre strength, e.g. interface failure.

The material presents a much stronger response in compression than in tension (Table 4 and Figure 4). This is likely to be due to the different failure modes at the constituent level, in the two cases. In tension, a sharp crack propagates in-plane, along an irregular path through the fibre-matrix interface and broken fibre segments (Figure 6.c). In compression, the failure mode is more diffuse (shear band) and propagates through-the-thickness (Figure 7) – so fibre-matrix interface failure and broken fibre segments play a reduced role.

Compressive failure

The compressive failure of the recycled composite is localised within inclined bands (Figure 7). This behaviour is also observed in virgin UD CFRPs [13]: under transverse compression a shear band is formed in the matrix, leading to the formation of a fracture plane oriented at an angle of 53° to the normal to the loading direction; under longitudinal compression, a kink-band – defined by high fibre-rotations and consequent failure within a band of sheared matrix – is developed, typically oriented at $\sim 20^\circ$ relatively to the normal to the loading direction. Similarities between these two features of virgin UD composites and the failure modes of the rCFRP do exist.

When some fibres are aligned with the load direction (Figures 7.a,c,e), failure resembles a kink-band. The random reinforcement architecture in the recycle provides a regular source of imperfections, and most of the fibres are broken in small segments; only matrix shearing and consequent fibre rotation within a band are necessary to have a failure mechanism similar to kink-band formation. Nevertheless, as the aligned fibres are considerably far away from each other, when no segments are already broken the bending induced by matrix shearing is not likely to be sufficient to promote fibre failure (Figure 7.a.2).

When most of the fibres are normal to the load direction (Figure 7.b), the damage band appears to affect only the matrix and the fibre-matrix interface.

As the rCFRP has a random reinforcement, a clear distinction between longitudinal and transverse failure modes cannot be done; instead, it is suggested that an intermediate mechanism occurs – closer to kink-band formation in areas relatively rich in

longitudinal fibres, and closer to transverse compression failure in areas relatively rich in transverse fibres. The orientations of the shear bands support the hypothesis of an intermediate failure mechanism. The lowest angle – 20° – is observed in Figure 7.a.1 (on the left), with the material compressed longitudinally (see zoom-in in Figure 7.a.2); this is approximately the typical angle in kink-band formation. The highest angle – 48° – is observed on the right in Figure 7.a.1, where barely any fibres are aligned with the loading direction; this is just slightly lower than the typical angle for UD composite transverse compressive failure.

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical behaviour of a recycled CFRP was investigated. The material has fibres reclaimed via pyrolysis, and was manufactured through a resin infusion of recycled-fibre mats. The reinforcement is in a randomly-oriented short-fibre architecture.

The material microstructure was observed. Fibres are mostly oriented within the laminate plane, and a slight preferred orientation along the manufacturing direction (longitudinal) was also observed. Some of the distinct features identified include variable fibre length, broken fibre segments, fibre waviness, fibres aggregated in bundles, and high void content.

The tensile and compressive mechanical properties were measured. The material is considerably stronger in compression than in tension, which was explained by the different failure mechanisms at the microscopic level; in addition, the preferred fibre orientation along the longitudinal manufacturing direction confers a significant orthotropic behaviour to the rCFRP.

The failure modes in tension and compression, both in the longitudinal and transverse directions, were investigated. Tensile failure occurs by in-plane crack propagation along fibre-matrix interface and fibre segments broken prior to loading. Compressive failure occurs by the formation of through-the-thickness shear bands of matrix and rotated fibres, in a mechanism with similarities both with kink-band formation and transverse compression failure in UD composites.

This study demonstrates the potential of rCFRP to replace GFRP (and eventually Aluminium) for structural applications. On the other hand, it shows that the failure mechanisms found in the recycle are different from those of its virgin precursor; even though transfer of phenomenological knowledge is possible, specific failure criteria and design methods for rCFRP need to be developed. Finally, the results suggest that, to improve the mechanical properties, it is necessary to (i) strengthen the fibre-matrix interface and (ii) reduce fibre breakage during composite manufacturing.

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References

1. Milled Carbon G. Marsh. Reclaiming value from post-use carbon composite. Reinforced Plastics, 2008.
2. EU Directive. End-of-life Vehicle Directive 2000/53/EC, 2000.
3. K.Schulte, L.O.Meyer. Closing the loop for CFRPs. ILA 2006.
4. J. Takahashi, N. Matsutsuka, T. Okazumi, et al. Mechanical properties of recycled CFRP by injection molding method. 16th ICCM, 2007.
5. S. J. Pickering. Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials – current status. Composites: Part A, vol. 36, 2006.
6. CFK Valley Stade Recycling GmbH & Co. KG.. CFRP Recycling Solutions. 2008.
7. R. E. Allred, J. M. Gosau, J. M. Shoemaker. Composite Recycling and Disposal – An Environmental R&D Issue. SAMPE 2001.
8. K. H. Wong, S. J. Pickering, T. A. Turner, N. A. Warrior, Preliminary Feasibility Study of Reinforcing Potential of Recycled Carbon Fibre for Flame-retardant Grade Epoxy Composite. Composites Innovation 2007 – Improved Sustainability and Environmental Performance, 2007.
9. B. Allen. Characterization of Reclaimed Carbon Fibers and their Integration into New Thermoset Polymer Matrices via Existing Composite Fabrication Techniques. Graduate Faculty of North Carolina State University, 2008.
10. K. H. Wong, S. J. Pickering, T. A. Turner, N. A. Warrior. Compression Moulding of a Recycled Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composite. SAMPE Conference, May 18-21, 2009, Baltimore, MD, 2009.
11. ASTM International. Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials, ASTM D 3039/D 3039M-00, Annual Book of ASTM Standards, 2000.
12. J. G. Haberle, E. W. Godwin. The Imperial College Method for Testing Composite Materials in Compression. The Composites Centre Technical Memo TM 93/03, 1993.
13. S. T. Pinho, L. Iannucci, P. Robinson. Physically based failure models and criteria for laminated fibre-reinforced composites with emphasis on fibre kinking. Part I: Development. Composites: Part A, 2006.